

The Future of E-Government: From One Stop Shop to No Stop Shop solution

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Abstract— Purpose: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the potential trends and issues faced in the development and adoption of e-government systems and the impact this will have on the future of e-government. The aim was to evaluate the progression of e-government systems from the one-stop-model characterized by offering government services online to a no-stop-model characterized by innovative governance. This will be marked by the development of future software development model for e-government systems.

Methods: An online desk research was conducted to identify secondary sources that outline the trends and issues faced by e-government systems. This will serve to inform any unmet needs and aspirations with existing models as well as opportunities and threats that should be anticipated in the design of e-government software models.

Findings: The research identified that there is an overarching need to enhance the participation and integration of public service delivery to make the process seamless, personalized, and proactive to future trends, opportunities, and threats. Hence, feature driven model is presented as an effective model to spark the development to a no-stop-shop model for e-government systems from the prevalent one-stop-shop model.

Conclusion: While there is a need for e-government systems to meet the functional objectives regarding offering public services, there is a need for the incorporated software model to future-proof the resultant e-government system to foreseeable and unforeseeable opportunities and threats.

Keywords: citizens, e-government, no-stop-shop, one-stop-shop, public services.

I. INTRODUCTION

Citizens and businesses alike will often interact with the government to receive public services. This is because, it is the mandate of the government to provide these services under the social contract upon which the premise of the government is founded upon. However, it is key to note that the delivery of these services is reliant on the collection and processing of data by the government [1]. Throughout time, this process has been continually streamlined especially with the adoption of technological advancements giving rise to e-government as a way to enhance the efficiency of public service delivery.

While there is no standard definition of e-government, the United Nations describes e-government as the utilization of ICTs to effectively and efficiently deliver public services to both citizens and businesses. However, it is key to note that it is only recently that e-government has entailed the utilization of ICTs since traditionally, e-government was overly focused on the provision of public services online. As such, e-government has evolved from being constrained to the perception of “online government services” to “innovation governance” marked by increased interactions and engagement between the government and the businesses and citizenry [2]. This outlines the aim of this paper, through the evaluation of the prevalent issues and trends and how this will influence the future of e-government a feature-driven software development model will be suggested as an effective and efficient way to drive the transition of e-government from a one-stop-shop to a no-stop-shop model.

The paper will be structured as follows; section 2 will present past literature relevant to the research topic. Section 3 will detail the implemented research design. Section 4 will then present a proposed model and the feature-driven model and how it aids in the transition from a one-stop-shop to a no-stop-shop. Section 5 will discuss how the new model will enhance e-government systems, especially, collection of requisite information and the subsequent delivery of a service. This will be achieved by mainly contextualizing it with existing research and models. Finally, section 6 will bring together all conclusions arrived at by the research inquiry.

II. BACKGROUND

According to [3] since the conceptualization of e-government in the 1990s, it has transformed public administration both from a cultural and organizational stance. This is because, the introduction of ICT and digital age technologies transformed the environment to an extent that it necessitated the governance systems to respond and evolve with this change [3]. It is important to note that the relationships and interactions between agents will usually influence the complex behavior in a system. With regard to this, it is posited that the association between ICT and government is co-evolutionary in that they both interact in a dynamic and changing environment.

From a public administration stance, the volatility of the environment and its evolutionary nature is evidenced by the

continued need for reforms at different levels of society. This understanding is furthered by [4] who outlines that the complexity of public administration is rooted in the realities of public administration. That is, it is carried out by numerous agencies and departments, it requires legislation and operating procedures outlined, as well as the continued adoption of requisite technologies. The co-evolutionary nature of both ICT and governance is then accurately described by [5] who outline that the existence of different forms and areas for the adoption of ICT have resulted in an increase in the variety of technologies with the capacity to further online administration. Governance then has to improve by adopting these technologies.

However, given the diversity of the areas and forms of application, it should be noted that the user of the platform determines the adoption and satisfaction of an e-government system. This is because, it is aimed at aiding every citizen to meet their human development needs. By extension, the design and adoption of e-government systems should be guided by an understanding of the needs of all public segments.

A. E-government models

Reference by [4] posit that online service delivery is at the core of e-government initiatives. Therefore, the development and deployment of systems that make this possible become a key priority. It is this that sets credence for the evaluation of methodologies, platforms and tools utilized in the e-government systems' software development process. As a result, several models have traditionally been used to create and develop e-government systems which offers insight into the steps of implementation used in developing the e-government system, and with it the aim of the system for public administration [6]. The first model, Layne and Lee, features four stages with the underlying aim being the creation of an integrated information base to bring about an integration of processes and functions on different levels of government. Hence, the transfer of these services to online channels creates a one-stop-shop model for accessing public services.

The next model, referred by [7] adds interactivity to the integrated information base. This not only allows for the public to receive government services but to also request them as they can now contact governmental officials and organizations online [6]. The next model, UN's (2001), advocates for public administration and its services to be accessed and provided seamlessly which necessitates all government agencies and departments function as a single and universal presence where citizens and other stakeholders access all kinds of services instantly and conveniently through one portal. In addition to ensuring the integration of all services, the Model of [8] introduces the participation phase that allows for voting services to be offered online and also allowing the public to post comments online [6]. Finally, the model of Wescott (2001) proposes a six-stage model that is an improvement from the previous as it allows for a joined-up government. Whereby, in addition to accessing all services on a web portal this model outlines that services and information are integrated to an extent that a user only identifies with the received services as they may

not necessarily know the involved government agency or department.

TABLE 1: FIVE MODELS OF E-GOVERNMENT

MODELS	PHASE 1	PHASE 2	PHASE 3	PHASE 4	PHASE 5	PHASE 6
Layne and Lee (2001)		Catalogue	Transaction	Vertical Integration	Horizontal Integration	
Baum and Di Maio (2000)	The Web Presence	Interaction	Transaction	Transformation		
UN's (2001)	Emerging Presence Web	Enhanced Presence	Interactive	Transaction Government	Seamless	
Hiller and Belanger (2001)		Information Dissemination	Two-way Communication	Transaction	Integration	Participation
Wescott (2001)	Email and Internal Work	Enabled Information Access to Information for Organizations and the Public	Two-way Communication	Exchange of Value	Digital Democracy	Joined-up Government

Source: Reference by [6]

B. The one-stop-shop model

Reference [9] outline that e-government is an attempt at modernizing public administration with the online one-stop-government being the first step on how that is achieved. This form of e-government is characterized by the integration of all public services to allow citizens and businesses to access public services from a single point even if the services are delivered by different departments or authorities. Reference by [1] defines "who asserts that without such a model, every department and authority would be contacted independently with a citizen or business having to distribute the needed data to every department or authority". Instead, this information is submitted to a single access point. Hence, from the perspective of a citizen, the one-stop-shop model is an integration of public services. On the other hand, the government perceives it as interconnectedness and interoperability of IT systems across its different agencies and departments.

However, while this is a key development its effectiveness and efficiency are significantly impacted by its reliance on forms and its reactivity. With regards to forms, while they are the primary interface for collecting information to deliver a service, they negatively impact the overall service delivery experience. This is because, filling the forms is cumbersome, repetitive whilst there is a risk of low comprehensibility. On the other hand, the reactivity of this model is rooted in the fact that service delivery is triggered by a citizen or a business and in each engagement, citizens will need to provide data. E-government models usually have five steps in common:

1. Publication of information on websites.
2. Communication with citizens via electronic channels.
3. Offering transaction services online.
4. Delivery of integrated e-government services.
5. E-Participation of citizens in decision making.

As one stop shops are commonly used, there are no proposals for possible extensions for these phased models. Therefore, to fill this gap the next step for governments is the transition from a one-stop shop to a no-stop shop. For a no stop-shop model to be designed, implemented, and assessed the three steps

approach has been taken.

The no-stop-shop-model is therefore presented as a natural solution to problems faced by the one-stop-shop model. That is, by transitioning from no-form service delivery towards proactive and ultimately predictive service delivery, it is possible to autonomously offer services and information that is both personalized and relevant to a citizen's life circumstances. Hence, for a no-stop-shop model service delivery is triggered by a life event occurrence or in anticipation of the occurrence of a life event. In either case, no request of a public service is made and by extension, it means no form is required to be filled before these services are received. Instead, citizens and businesses alike receive them as recommendations and features personalized to the prevalent life realities.

III. METHODS

This research inquiry relied on secondary sources to identify the trends and issues for e-government systems and the development process, and as a result infer the future of e-government. That is, through online desk research, this research identified journal articles, web articles, books, government publications among other sources to determine user-level factors that influence the development and adoption of e-government systems. This was followed by the determination of gaps that a future software development model should address which led to the conceptualization of a model.

A. *An Approach to No-Stop-Shop*

Firstly, the first draft of the phase model based in the research context is built on an established Theory of the phase and related work on forms, constructive government, and data integration. The stage model is refined iteratively in discussions in a group of four researchers.

Second, two semi-structured interviews were conducted. The aim of the interviews was to provide an initial insight into the validity and scale of the model, the government's current strategy for implementing a no-stop shop and the anticipated challenges and opportunities for implementing a no-stop shop.

Third, a number of further interviews were conducted with practitioners to sharpen the model and to validate its face and gain initial insights into the possible problems which would impede progress towards a 'no-stop-shop' for further understanding of the context.

There are three dimensions of no-stop shop. First "Integration of Data Collection" refers to and managing forms. Citizens benefit from an integrated data collection because information must be submitted exclusively to a single entity and the repeated entry of same information in various forms is not necessary. Governments also benefits from integrated data collection by increasing the data quality and decreased effort to manage forms that result from a reduced additional form length. It should, however, be stored regardless of how the data reaches the government. So, the second stage refers to "Integration of Data Storage". This dimension addresses data processing within and through governments.

For two reasons, an integrated data storage is useful: Firstly, it allows removal of forms or decreases the complexity of a form when it is not possible to fully remove them. Secondly, the incorporation of data storage is a crucial third-dimensional facilitator that reflects on how data are used. In particular it enables analysis of proactive services which are activated by the government and predictive services before the fact, after the fact, and by the administration. This will make possible proactive and predictive service delivery which is the highest point on the third dimension. Lastly the third dimension "Purpose of Data Use" is used which refers to the use of stored and organized data. These dimensions are used to provide insights into how government service delivery can progress through the stages "One-Stop-Shop", "Limited No-Stop-Shop" and "No-Stop-Shop". The "No-Stop Shop" is characterized for the proactive and predictive delivery of the service and is characterized as an extension of "One-Stop Shop." This results in the delivery of public services without any intervention taken by the citizen. We propose an intermediary stage called the "Limited No-Stop-Shop" before enforcing the final No-Stop-Shop which still depends on forms. During this point, the administration carries out proactive or predictive delivery, thereby reducing the acts the citizen carries out.

To conclude, while the objective of a 'one-stop shop' is to decrease the number of forms by integration of the front end, a 'no-stop shop' seeks to avoid an exchange of information between the people and the government. The "one stop shop" idea considers the form as a central component of the provision of government services and acts as the sole touch point for citizens — the "no stop shop" removes this point of contact and therefore all aspects of the provision of state services.

The No-Stop shop uses two ways, for this reason, to fulfil the two purposes of forms and serve as alternatives, integrated storage of data to make available all the data needed and a constructive, predictive model to predict whether a citizen requires a service before a citizen asks for a service. It does not contribute to "No-Shop" just supporting one of the two: If missing information is required or the customer has to send a service delivery form.

B. *Proposed model*

By relying on agile development, feature-driven development was identified as the best approach to build a proactive and predictive system and by evaluating the available digital technological capabilities and existing frameworks a conceptual model on how these capabilities can be capitalized on to address the existing gaps with the prevalent models was presented. Past literature was also used to support how the proposed feature-driven e-government model was aligned with the future of e-government both in terms of development and utilization, specifically, the advancement from a one-stop-shop model to a no-stop-shop model for public service delivery.

First, it is key to outlined that FDD is an agile development approach and as such, its software development approach is grounded on iterative development. What is more, as a basic

requirement, the scope and requirements have to be laid down before the development process. Central to agile development, the number of iterations, duration and scope of each are also defined in advance. Finally, it should be noted that each iteration will involve a team that goes through the full software development lifecycle before a working product can be developed and demonstrated.

Lynn (2021) posits that FDD is innately customer-centric, iterative and incremental that is focused on delivering tangible results often and efficiently. By reducing both confusion and rework, it becomes superior model as the project can be regularly updated and errors can be identified quickly. It makes it ideal for long-term and complex projects. This grounds the rationale behind using FDD as the underlying model. That is, the complexity is due to the manner that public services are delivered, by different agencies and departments whereas the longevity of development is as a result of the co-evolutionary nature shared by ICT technologies and governance mechanisms. FDD was chosen because of its customer-centrism which is important since both the adoption and satisfaction of e-government systems is determined by the end-user. Moreover, since flexibility and proactivity are what are needed to improve e-government while enhancing overall alignment future trends and capacity to respond to the changing needs and aspirations of the citizenry, a feature-driven approach is effective in ingraining these competencies in e-government systems.

Therefore, the development phases will be structured as iterations which means their design and development will follow the steps set out by FDD, these are, gathering data, developing the overall model, building a feature list, planning by feature, designing by feature and finally, building by feature.

Figure 1: Feature Driven Development Phases

- Developing an overall model – This step will involve detailing the problem the software development project should solve. In addition to aiding in the definition of context and scope for the system, it serves as an outline for the entire phase.
- Building a feature list – This step will evaluate the functional value of the e-government at every phase to determine the flexibility and proactivity gaps. This will inform the features that should be introduced at each phase.
- Planning by feature – From the identified features, this will entail determining the needed resources to actualize each phase.
- Designing by feature – In this step, different stakeholders will be involved to determine the technical and framework specifics as well as the feature priorities for every phase.
- Building by feature – In this final step, all the needed items that support the design are implemented, these are, the user interface, technical components, and a module for each phase is

made available for testing and approval.

C. Stages

Overall, the aim of the model is to ensure the transition of e-government from its current one-stop-shop and embrace a no-stop-shop model. However, considering the complexity of governance and the changing nature of public administration, several changes have to be made at different levels to create an enabling environment for the needed competencies to be introduced and others enhanced. As aforementioned, each stage after requirement definition will be considered an iterative stage, and as a result, their development will take on an FDD approach by adhering to the steps. Therefore, the overall model is driven by the objective of not only making the government suggest services but it goes on to become an initiator of a public service. For instance, the government can start rolling out the pension funds when one gets to the legal retirement age. This is without the citizen having to ask for the pension funds. Hence, each phase will focus on how to enhance its proactive and predictive capacity and how to continually enhance it.

PHASE	DESCRIPTION
Requirement definition	This phase will require developing an understanding of the needs and aspirations of businesses, citizens, and communities within a jurisdiction. This will underly the development process whereby, the objectives of the system will be aligned with these needs and aspirations as well as the human development needs.
Collaborative design and development	Collaborative involvement of representatives from the constituent groups will be important to evaluate the usability, efficiency, and effectiveness of the system. This is aimed at ensuring information and service gaps are effectively addressed.
Joined up government	This will focus on ensuring the vertical and horizontal integration of government departments, agencies, and functions to a single, interactive and seamless system.
Monitoring and participation	This will allow for democratic, transactional interaction with the government in its entirety. It shall allow for feedback on service delivery among other aspects of the e-government system to inform future development/improvement efforts.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RECOMANDATIONS

As outlined by [10] and [11] digital technology are important in the development of smart societies which are characterized by the thoughtful deployment of digital technologies by the government to improve the welfare of citizens, economic stability, and institutional effectiveness. In this regard, technology becomes an avenue to attain these objectives. Reference [12] goes on to outline that government leaders are increasingly being evaluated with regards to the benefits they create for the constituents, who comprise citizens, communities, and businesses. Just like typical clients, these groups expect top performance and efficiency, the delivery of better service and results, public trust, and appropriate accountability. When this is coupled up with the fact that novel aspirations of citizens are resulting in novel demands on governments around the world, key among them being the need for transparency, efficiency, and enhanced performance [12], [11].

Therefore, the feature-driven model is uniquely aligned to result in the development of a smart society. By imbuing public service delivery with the capacity to autonomously offer government services proactively and predictively, this will enhance overall welfare of citizens and businesses. Finally, as [6] asserts that most governments are interested in e-government initiatives to ensure efficient provision of public services, enhance engagement between citizens and the state, ensure the integrity of information between government agencies. This model will allow for this since the outcome is a flexible system capable of allowing for the quick adaptation to the changing needs and social realities. Hence, as aforementioned earlier, while service delivery has traditionally been subsequent to the collection of information, the feature-driven model will serve to do away with the necessity of information collection, instead, a record is made existent autonomously following one's birth and is continuously updated both autonomously and from the different points of contact that will exist between an individual and the government.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to evaluate the potential trends and issues of e-government and their influence on the future of e-government, specifically how the one-stop model will evolve towards a no stop model. We propose a model stage where we will create a digital form in which the citizens will get access only to their concerned feature whereas the government will have access to their required information. The purpose of introducing this model is to avoid the hassle of multiple forms as well as provide a distinction between government and citizen's related data in a single database. The form will be customizable therefore can be transformed according to the requirements of the offered services. Since the access will be given according to the needs of the user, boundaries for the dimensions will be created.

The proposed feature-driven model allows for this progression as it sets out a path how e-government systems should be designed to ensure flexibility and proactivity is an inherent competence. The importance of this is that the resultant system can be continually tweaked to fit the changing needs and aspirations as well as the prevalent social realities. Therefore, as the opportunities for the implementation of ICT in governance continue to evolve and the needs and aspirations of constituents continue to change, an inherent need to transcend the provision of public services as a central premise for e-governments and adopt a more active role in the life of constituents is presented. To attain this, there is a need to enhance an understanding of the constituents and personalize service delivery which ought to direct the design and development of e-government systems.

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